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Spatio-temporal dynamics of urban space and land pressure in Houndé, a gold-mining area in Burkina Faso

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to analyse the contribution of gold mining to urban sprawl in the city of Houndé. Primary and secondary data were used for this purpose. The study revealed strong urban demographic growth in Houndé, as well as various modes of land acquisition, tools and urban development operations as characteristics and factors of urban dynamics. From an urbanisation rate of 1.36% in 1996, the city of Houndé rose to 1.24% in 2006, then 1.6% in 2019. The city is expanding very rapidly (55%), and there is also a high concentration of the population of Houndé (51%), with 84% of this population living in unparcelled areas of the city and only 14% living in parceled areas. The cartographic analysis shows an impressive evolution of the urban space of Houndé, with an area increasing from 1,459.43 ha in 2012 to 1,826.85 ha in 2016, representing a spatial increase of 25.26% in four years. In 2021, the city's area was 5,145.84 ha, representing an increase of 3,318.99 ha over the five years between 2016 and 2021, or 181.67%. The local population and farmers perceive the cost of living in Houndé to be high (45%), with housing problems (41%) and land pressure (14%) also being issues. It would therefore be wise for the municipal and state authorities to take action to promote sustainable urbanisation of gold-mining towns.

Keywords: Spatio-temporal, dynamics, Urban space, Land pressure, Area gold-mining, city of Houndé, Burkina Faso

1. INTRODUCTION

Gold mining is now the main driver of urbanisation and the dynamics of urban areas in certain cities around the world. Gold mining also impacts agricultural growth, other socio-economic activities and even urban areas (Chuhan-Pole & al., 2020; Gagnol et al., 2019; Büscher & al., 2014; Tapsoba et al., 2023 and Bohbot, 2017). This is specifically the case for the city of Chami in Mauritania, according to Gagnol & al. (2019); for the city of Kivu in the DRC, according to Büscher & al. (2014) and the towns of Gaoua and Kampti in Burkina Faso, according to Bohbot (2017).

Gold mining began in Burkina Faso in the 15th century. The severe droughts of 1974 and 1984, as well as the two locust invasions of 1974 and 1975 that destroyed crops, led people to turn to gold panning as a means of resilience in Burkina Faso, particularly in the north of the country. As a result, the mining sector in Burkina Faso has experienced spectacular growth since the 1980s, with a boom that has seen the arrival of large mining companies (Raharisoa, 2021).

These are major mining companies such as I AM GOLD ESSAKANE, SEMAFO (Mining company in West Africa) and BISSA Gold. This is due to the adoption of a new mining code on 8 May 2003, revised on 26 June 2015, which offers sufficient advantages for mining exploration and exploitation. Today, a significant number of large industrial mining companies have also emerged.

This is the case for Endeavour Mining and its affiliates (Houndé Gold Operation SA; Bouéré-Dohoun Gold Operation SA); Sanbrado Mining Company (SOMISA) SA; Société TOEGA SA and the large Inata gold mine of Société Afro Turc Inata SA.

Thanks to the blessing of a bill allowing the revision of Law No. 036-2015/CNT of 26 June 2015 on the mining code of Burkina Faso and its amendment, Law No. 012-2023/ALT of 25 July 2023. This review aims to provide a solid and up-to-date legal instrument to better regulate the mining sector and generate revenue for the State (Alexandrov and Iablonev, 2018). Burkina Faso's traditional cotton industry saw its leading export product change in 2010.

Yellow gold replaced white gold in the country's economy. The same is true for the town of Houndé, where gold mining has become the main driver of income and development for the population over the last ten years (Bazillier et al., 2020). The gold rush has had adverse socio-economic and environmental effects, but it has also stimulated the local and national economy (Kalamandeen, 2019; Kaku & al., 2021).

The extraction of gold is a source of income, strong demographics, land investment and urban dynamism, which generates enormous demand for both rural and urban land (Toure, 2000; Soma & al., 202; Gagnol & al., 2021).

Specifically, the urban area of Houndé is undergoing rapid expansion, posing enormous problems for local authorities in terms of land use planning and urban space management. Urban planning operations in Burkina Faso, as in Houndé, are not keeping pace with the evolution and development of cities, leading to the proliferation of unplanned peri-urban neighbourhoods.

This situation raises the following research question: how does gold mining contribute to urban sprawl in the city of Houndé? The study aims to analyse the contribution of gold mining to urban sprawl in the city of Houndé.

The research hypothesis is that gold mining, due to its high demographic migration and large investors, promotes urban sprawl in the city of Houndé.

2. METHOD AND STUDY AREA

2. 1. The study area

The study area Houndé is the capital of Tuy Province, one of the provinces of the Hauts-Bassins region, whose regional capital is Bobo-Dioulasso. Covering an area of 2.18 km², the town of Houndé is bordered to the east by the rural commune of Boni, to the west by the village of Bouéré, to the north-west by the village of Dohoun and to the north by the village of Tiomboni (Figure 1). According to the 2019 RGPH¹, the city has a population of 87,151 inhabitants and an economy based on agriculture and gold mining. Indeed, the wealth of yellow ore in the subsoil of Houndé has led to the development of mining and artisanal activities in the Tuy area. Services, trade and crafts are also important.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the study area.

2. 2. Data collection and processing techniques

This study is based on a review of the literature, surveys, interviews, and direct observations in the field. The literature review was conducted in the central library of Joseph KI-ZERBO University (BCUJKZ), the digital library of Cheick Anta DIOP University (BNUCAD), the library of the Institute for Research and Development (IRD) and on search engines such as Google Scholar and Cairn.info. This literature review focused on reports,

¹ General population and housing census

dissertations, theses, scientific articles, and books related to gold mining and urban dynamics in gold-bearing areas.

The interviews involved seven resource persons, including local authorities, former mayors, the president of the special delegation, and real estate developers. The household surveys involved 384 people and were determined using Schwartz's probabilistic method (1995).

The formula used by this method is: $Tme = [(Z\beta)^2 \times P (1-P) /d^2]$; where (Tme) is the minimum sample size to be surveyed. (Zβ) is the confidence interval, which is 95% and corresponds to a standard value of 1.96. (P) is the standard proportion, such as the rate of a population that has a specific characteristic among a set of possible characteristics.

As this proportion is unknown in this study, it will be estimated at 50% to determine the average sample size and finally deduce the sampling rate. (d) represents the tolerated margin of error. The tolerated margin of error is between +/-5%.

AN: $Tme = [(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)] / (0.05)^2$ therefore $Tme = 384$

We used demographic data from the 2019 General Population and Housing Census (RGPH). The number of households surveyed in each sector is determined in proportion to the total number of households in the sector according to the quota formula:

$N = (Xi \times Tme) / X$

where: N is the number of households surveyed per sector. Xi is the total number of households in each sector, Tme is the minimum sample size, and X is the total number of households in the urban commune.

With a total population of 87,151 and 17,409 households in 2019. The results are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Total households surveyed broken down by sector.

Urban commune of Houndé	Housekeeping	Populations	Households to be surveyed
Sector 1	782	3 650	17,24
Sector 2	3 332	13 851	73,49
Sector 3	4 983	24 907	109,91
Sector 4	6 261	31 828	138,18
Sector 5	2 051	12 915	45,24
Total	17 409	87 151	384,06

Source: RGPH², 2019

² General population and housing census

For data processing and analysis, Microsoft Office Excel 2013 was used for tables and graphs. Google Earth Pro was used for digitisation and spatialisation of geographical entities. QGIS 3.16 software was used to produce the maps included in this study.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Characteristics of urban spatial-temporal dynamics

The characterisation of territorial dynamics depends on the determinants of land occupation and use. These include demographics, land acquisition methods, urban planning tools and operations (geographical and land use planning framework). The issue of urban territorial dynamics is global and remains quite significant in cities in Burkina Faso.

These dynamics are particularly pronounced in developing countries that lack the necessary tools and means to control urban spaces. Urban territorial development is a multidimensional process that involves the confrontation of individual or collective preferences regarding the allocation of territorial resources (land, natural spaces, natural resources) to alternative uses. Urban sprawl, the persistence of peripheral neighbourhoods and rapid urbanisation are therefore the main concerns of the urban authorities in Houndé in the wake of the proliferation of gold mining (Figure 2 below).

Figure 2. Urban sprawl.
Source: Field survey, September 2022.

Like other cities in Burkina Faso, the urban commune of Houndé has experienced rapid urbanisation in recent decades. Indeed, the urbanisation rate rose from 1.36% in 1996 to 1.24% in 2006, then to 1.6% in 2019. Thus, availability, modes of acquisition, new land actors,

accessibility to land, operations and development tools are the fundamental elements promoting territorial dynamics. According to Figure 2 below, 96% of respondents say that the city has spread out.

3. 2. Factors of spatial dynamics and land pressure in Houndé

This study examines the impact of gold mining on urban territorial dynamics, knowledge of the city and the flows that drive it. Population dynamics, socio-economic activities, the economic benefits of gold mining and the structuring of urban space are all factors that promote spatial dynamics. These factors also influence the relationship between gold mining and land needs. Their implications, when viewed in depth, provide essential data for measuring the effects of improved living conditions and land pressure. Land is an indispensable resource for human well-being and urban development, making it the focus of our research. A retrospective look at the various urban development operations that have taken place and the problems they have caused allows us to say that urban development and urban planning tools are also factors in spatial dynamics. According to Figure 3 below, the city of Houndé is expanding very rapidly (55%), 27% think that this urban sprawl is rapid and 12% see it as moderate, compared to only 6% who consider the city's expansion to be slow.

Figure 3. Rate of urban sprawl in the city of Houndé.

Source: Field survey, September 2022.

According to respondents, the reasons for the sprawl of the city of Houndé are the development of peripheral neighbourhoods, scattered construction throughout the city, the affordable cost of land in outlying neighbourhoods, the scarcity of development projects, and the city's high population growth.

3. 3. The structure and distinctive features of the city of Houndé

The urban commune of Houndé, given its location and status, is favoured over other communes in the province. Since colonial times, the city has benefited from development projects, the provision of social services, and other infrastructure. Thus, the Houndé agglomeration consists of developed areas and undeveloped areas called peripheral neighbourhoods.

Its location on National Road No. 1 (RN1) and the establishment of two SOFITEX ginning factories make Houndé an important centre of attraction and exchange in the province. It has grown from a small town to become the capital of the province of Tui. It is also the seat of local government following the decentralisation and division of the province orchestrated by the Burkinabe state in 1995. Houndé is therefore the municipality that has benefited most from the economic spin-offs of gold mining, but also the one that has suffered most from the negative effects of gold mining in the province of Tui. This explains the pressure on land in the urban municipality of Houndé. The urban area has experienced rapid demographic and economic growth and urbanisation. The city has seen significant agricultural immigration motivated by the agricultural potential of the land and rainfall. The area has a wet season of 5 to 6 months, so it is well watered with an average annual rainfall of between 800 and 900 mm. Added to this is the development of commercial activities, industries and the gold rush.

In addition, the high birth rate, with a crude birth rate (CBR) of 46.3‰, has created a significant urban population boom in Houndé. The need for land is becoming a real concern in terms of providing housing for urban populations. Indeed, population growth generates land needs, which in turn generate territorial dynamics. Thus, territorial dynamics raise the question of the recomposition of the occupation and use of territorial units as well as the concentration of the population of Houndé (Figure 4 below). This concentration is described as very high (51%), high (32%), medium (14%) and low by 3% of the population surveyed.

Figure 4. Rate of population concentration in the city of Houndé.
Source: Field survey, September 2022.

The same population surveyed believes that this very high concentration is observed in unparcelled areas (86%) compared to 14% who consider it to be in parceled areas.

All these ongoing processes are considered to be a source of imbalance, situated at the intersection of several types of preferences for users of land, landscapes and territorial resources. These preferences include the 'living environment' function for residents, the productive function for agricultural, industrial or service companies, local authorities and developers, and conservation preferences expressed by environmental protection movements. The multiple functions associated with land therefore require the competent authorities to organise and develop urban space.

3. 4. The developed area of the city of Houndé

The developed area of the city of Houndé covers three sectors, namely sectors 2 and 3 and a large part of sector 4, representing 20% of the city (Houndé Town Hall Land Department, 2022 and field survey, 2022). Sectors 1 and 5 of Houndé have never undergone any development operations. This is because these sectors were villages attached to the urban commune of Houndé, which mainly consisted of sectors 2, 3 and 4. However, developing these sectors could have alleviated the housing shortage to some extent, reduced the lack of plots in developed areas and curbed the proliferation of undeveloped areas.

In 1957, the colonial administration, with a view to offering building land to alleviate housing problems, carried out a subdivision, which was the very first subdivision in Houndé. This first development operation created 257 plots and concerned sectors 2 and 3. Sector 2 was the neighbourhood of the first inhabitants of Houndé. It is one of the indigenous and royal neighbourhoods, but also the neighbourhood of the chief of the land. Sector 3, meanwhile, housed some colonial administrative buildings. The second phase of subdivision took place in 1987 and created 686 plots, again in sectors 2 and 3. Sector 4 underwent its first subdivision operation in 1999, during which 4,000 plots were created to reduce the need for plots. In total, the three phases of land subdivision in the urban commune of Houndé only created around 5,000 plots. Figure 5 below shows the structure of the three phases of land subdivision in the town. The urban space will be completed with the creation of commercial, industrial, leisure and residential areas, 10 land reserves (RF) and 19 administrative reserves (RA); 1 land domain (DF); 9 green spaces (EV); 2 markets and places of worship.

Field surveys have shown that only a minority of the population of Houndé lives in subdivided areas. This situation is both a result of and an indicator of poverty, the lack of and poor spatial orientation of urban development operations by politicians offering plots in low-lying areas. Only the wealthiest can therefore invest in these low-lying areas. After the last land subdivision operation in the city of Houndé, 20 years ago, only the mining company Endeavour Mining has built three resettlement sites for people affected³ by relocation operations. These are located in Koho sector No. 5, Bouéré and Kari. These housing estates have made it possible to develop 458 plots of land for the benefit of approximately 2,340 people. The estates are inhabited at an average of around 75% of their capacity (Endeavour's senior management).

In addition to the Endeavour mining company, certain real estate developers are also involved. For example, the real estate company ESA Services Immo has acquired approximately 140 hectares with a view to creating 2,000 plots, reserves and green spaces in the Bobi neighbourhood in sector no. 3.

³ People whose fields were taken away by the mine during the process of setting up and running the mine.

Figure 5. The different phases of the Houndé town development.

The real estate company Expertis has obtained 50 hectares in sector No. 5 to develop 800 plots. Général Immobilier, for its part, has obtained an area for development, the size of which remains unknown. Finally, as part of President Rock Marc Christian KABORE's 40,000 housing project, the State has acquired 25 hectares in sector No. 5 in Koho. All these actions are aimed at making plots and housing estates available to resolve housing issues in Houndé. It should be noted that the plots released by these various phases of development are not being developed in the town of Houndé.

3. 5. The population's perception of the high cost of housing and living in Houndé

One of the dreams of the inhabitants of the city of Houndé is to have access to a residential plot of land. However, this dream may seem utopian, given that such access remains difficult. Indeed, rapid population growth has led to high demand for housing and high prices for housing and plots of land. In addition, the scarcity of development projects has exacerbated the conditions for accessing land in developed areas and housing in general in Houndé. All these factors have led the population to settle in informal neighbourhoods in the city of Houndé. Sectors 2, 3 and 4, which have not been fully developed, constitute a large part of the city's undeveloped areas. The urban sprawl of the city of Houndé is very noticeable and is a fairly crucial issue.

Figure 6. Main impacts of gold mining in Houndé.

Source: Field survey, September 2022.

The inhabitants of Houndé saw the arrival of the mine in the city as a way out. However, they were unpleasantly surprised to find that gold mining has led to a high cost of living at all levels without exception, including land and access to housing. For example, two-room houses (a living room, a bedroom and a kitchen) that used to cost 25,000 CFA francs per month now

cost 50,000 CFA francs, and those that used to cost 30,000 CFA francs now cost 60,000 CFA francs. For one-bedroom houses (where the kitchen is integrated into the main room), rents have risen from 15,000 CFA francs to 30,000 CFA francs per month. Landlords are increasing rents without warning: if you cannot pay, you have to leave, and the miners will come and take your place. This exorbitant increase in costs in Houndé does not only affect rents. For other basic necessities, since the mine was established, from the exploration phase to the exploitation phase, the cost of living has become extremely high in Houndé (Figure 6 below).

To illustrate the high cost (45%) shown in Figure 6 above, 'what could be earned at 100 CFA francs has risen to 200 CFA francs, and what could be earned at 500 CFA francs has risen to 1,000 CFA francs, much to the dismay of the population,' said Traore Adama, president of the Houndé citizen watch committee. According to the survey in 2022, civil servants have left their homes in Houndé because they saw landlords double their rents overnight. The cost of residential land has also changed, and rents have varied. This variation also depends on whether the area is subdivided or not. The variation in these amounts, compared to the income of an average inhabitant, also justifies the proliferation of informal settlements, which are a visible facet of the problem of land pressure.

3. 6. The proliferation of peripheral neighbourhoods and the uncontrolled spread of Houndé

Since November 2014, the Burkinabe government has suspended urban development operations, while the population continues to grow. The analysis in Figure 7 below shows that in 2012, the city of Houndé had an area of 1,458.43 ha. This period was dominated by agriculture, livestock farming, Sofitex activities, trade and gold panning. After this period, gold mining boomed in the Houndé area, with all its consequences. The town of Houndé underwent impressive expansion, with its area increasing from 1,459.43 ha in 2012 to 1,826.85 ha in 2016.

This represents a spatial increase of 25.26% in area over four years. This date corresponds to the year of construction and installation of the industrial mine in Houndé. According to estimates by the Houndé town hall in 2017, the population has increased by 62,910 people in just eight years. This has resulted in the expansion of urban space, with strong action and demand for land by new players.

According to the analysis in Figure 7 above, in just four years, the city has expanded by 368.42 hectares. In 2017, with the start of the massive influx of people and new land investors to Houndé thanks to the effective establishment of the industrial mine but also to increased gold panning. In 2021, the area of Houndé was measured at 5,145.84 hectares. Referring to the area in 2016, we see an increase of 3,318.99 hectares over the five years, or 181.67%. This is the period following the establishment and official opening of HGO. Since then, the race for land has intensified in Houndé under the influence of various investments.

Its land investments are mainly focused on the construction of modern housing (hotels, inns and leisure centres), commercial use and other types of investments. The city's surface area between 2012 and 2021 shows an increase of 3,687.41 hectares in just nine years, representing a spatial increase of 252.83%. A major factor that can be added to gold mining to explain this significant spatial growth is the insecurity that has led to the arrival in Houndé of approximately 15,000 internally displaced persons (IDPs) meeting with the mayor of Houndé in 2023.

In general, we can say that the expansion of the city of Houndé has taken place in all four cardinal directions. In the north-south direction, the expansion is tapered. However, the city's expansion has mainly taken place in the east-west direction (Figure 7 below).

Figure 7. Evolution of undeveloped space in the city of Houndé

The significant spread from east to west in Houndé can be explained by the availability of developable and habitable land. It can also be explained by the 1999 and 2002 land subdivision, which was devoted solely to sector 4 of the city of Houndé. It was guided by the policy of the local authorities at the time.

3. 7. The issue of urban development in the city of Houndé

Moreover, certain sectors of the city have never been subject to a subdivision operation. The sectors that have benefited from previous land subdivision are not entirely subdivided. They are the least densely populated, but also lack infrastructure of all kinds. Sector No. 5, which houses the Endeavour mine processing site, has seen the arrival of a few property developers. The mine and the State have acquired land in this sector for development. According to former Mayor M BOUE Yazon, Houndé was composed of two large entities, the city centre (developed area)⁴ and the attached villages (undeveloped area)⁵. Attached in May 1987, the two sectors (Karaba and Koho), which were located outside the urban core, were not part of the city centre of Houndé. They were established as sectors in 1999 during the subdivision of sector No. 4. Karaba then became sector No. 1 and Koho sector No. 5.

The areas of these two sectors, Binté and Karabassira, are therefore potential development areas to relieve congestion⁶ in the undeveloped neighbourhoods. Of the 2.8 km² that make up the city, only 28% of the territory is developed, with the remaining 72% still undeveloped.

It is true that a tributary of the Mouhoun River divides the city of Houndé into two parts. Occupying this area for housing requires significant resources, which are therefore inaccessible, especially to the less well-off. During the rainy season, water rises from the minor bed of the tributary to the major bed, flooding the nearest dwellings. This appears to be a limitation to the development of the city. However, this tributary would be a real asset for the city if only it had a development plan. Field surveys show that land pressure in Houndé is a real problem.

But according to 67% of those surveyed, it is due to several reasons, including the suspension of housing developments by the Burkinabe government, rapid urbanisation, the exorbitant cost of plots in developed areas, and the affordable cost of land in undeveloped areas. For 33% of respondents, land pressure is linked to a lack of financial resources and spatial planning tools such as the land use plan (POS) and the urban development master plan (SDAU) for the city of Houndé. Land pressure is also linked to poor policy guidance in the last phase of land subdivision, which made plots available in low-lying areas. Many of the people who owned land in this area had to sell their plots and move to undeveloped areas because they could not afford to build in the area.

4. DISCUSSION

Our discussion will focus on three points, namely the characteristics and factors of spatial dynamics, the high cost of living and housing, the proliferation of peripheral neighbourhoods and the issue of urban development in the city of Houndé.

⁴ The city centre consisted of five districts: Bouakuy, Moumini, Koéré, Lokihoun, Binté and Boby.

⁵ The attached villages are: Karaba, currently sector no. 1, and Koho, currently sector no. 5.

⁶ To clear a place of what is cluttering it, according to the Larousse French Dictionary 1.04.

4. 1. Characteristics and factors of spatial dynamics

The characteristics of urban spatial dynamics include high population growth, land requirements driven by their mode of acquisition, and urban planning tools and operations, i.e. the geographical framework and land use planning. Our study area is experiencing urban sprawl, according to 96% of respondents, compared to 4% who are unaware of this urban sprawl. The results we have obtained in this study are similar to those of Fanchette & al. (2015); Deborah & al. (2022) et Valea (2024), who in their works show that territorial dynamics are a function of land occupation and use determinants. These results are also confirmed by Rouamba & al. (2024); Gough & al. (2019), who found that gold mining contributes significantly to the dynamics of land occupation units and thus to territorial dynamics. According to SNADDT⁷ (2017), territorial dynamics are a global phenomenon but are particularly significant in Burkina Faso.

They are also a multidimensional process involving the confrontation of individual or collective preferences, according to Philippe and Kirat (2005); Marcel & al. (2016).

4. 2. High housing and living costs in gold mining areas

In urban gold mining areas, demand for housing is not proportional to supply given the large number of city dwellers in these areas. Added to this is the scarcity of housing production due to local authority policies. The cost of renting houses has skyrocketed since the industrial mine was established in Houndé. Two-bedroom houses (bedroom, living room and kitchen) have gone from 25,000 CFA francs to 50,000 CFA francs and from 30,000 CFA francs to 60,000 CFA francs. Similarly, the cost of land for residential use in gold-mining areas varies depending on whether it is in a subdivided or unsubdivided neighbourhood.

Simonneau (2017) found in his work that the variation in housing and land costs compared to the income of an average inhabitant justifies the proliferation of informal settlements. Fanchette S. et al. (2015) also found in their work that the price of 400 to 500 m² plots is around 7,000,000 CFA francs when they are in a well-developed and accessible area. According to Chatel & al. (2017), the factors that influence the cost of rent are mainly the type of neighbourhood and construction, the intensity of demand, the cost of the plot and the condition of the house. The pace of urban growth was correlated with the creation of residential plots and the production of housing in order to offset the exorbitant cost of housing (Sainteny, 2008). As for the high cost of living, one respondent stated, 'Everything that used to cost 100 CFA francs in Houndé now costs 200 CFA francs, and what used to cost 500 CFA francs now costs 1,000 CFA francs, much to the dismay of the population.' The respondent added that, in addition to the prices of goods, landlords have also increased rents.

4. 3. The proliferation of peripheral neighbourhoods and the problem of urban planning in the city of Houndé

The results of this study showed that the city of Houndé, which is largely undeveloped (72% of the urban area), is home to more than the city's population. This has led to the sprawl of the city since the mining boom in the area. Poor populations migrate to the outskirts in order to obtain a plot of land at an affordable cost, resulting in significant gentrification in mining towns. Land is a business opportunity for a certain category of city dwellers, as it is a sure

⁷ National Plan for Sustainable Land Use and Development (SNADDT) 2040

means of access to wealth, particularly for speculators keen to secure their fortunes (Fanchette & al., 2015). Land sales generally increase with the blessing of brokers in gold-producing areas (Tarrouth & Colin, 2016). The methods of granting, acquiring and managing land, as well as land sales, contribute to the proliferation of peripheral neighbourhoods (Zougouri et Mathieu, 2001).

According to the work of Rouamba S. & al. (2025), the gold boom in a city increases the demand for land for investment in housing and infrastructure for the benefit of the population.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The use of a mixed method (quantitative and qualitative data) made it possible to understand the population's perception of urban territorial dynamics in gold-mining areas.

In general, in mining areas, the characteristics of urban dynamics include demographics (high migration and birth rates), land acquisition methods (sale, donation and inheritance), tools (POS and SDAU) and development operations (subdivisions and others). Between 2010 and 2022, 608 residential and commercial plots were transferred by sale and 206 by inheritance in Houndé. The annual average number of plots transferred by sale is 46.77 and 15.85 plots by inheritance. As for the urban sprawl of Houndé, it can be noted that the city has experienced a significant increase in its surface area. The subdivided part of the city was 2.18 km² until 2000. However, this surface area has remained unchanged to this day, but the non-subdivided part has undergone significant changes before, during and after the mining boom in Houndé. In 2012, the undeveloped area of the city covered 1,458.43 ha, with gold panning as the dominant type of exploitation. In 2016, the urban (undeveloped) area of Houndé increased slightly to 1,826.85 ha, an increase of 368.42 ha.

This period corresponds to the establishment of the Houndé industrial mine. We are therefore witnessing two types of gold mining (gold panning and industrial). After the mine was established between 2016 and 2021, the urban area of Houndé expanded considerably, reaching 5,145.84 ha, an increase of 3,318.99 ha in five years and an increase of 3,687.41 ha in nine years. These urban area figures were obtained using Google Earth Pro to digitise the city limits in 2012, 2016 and 2021. We concluded that mining areas are undergoing rapid urbanisation, which poses challenges in terms of planning, housing and land market value. The study also shows that the cost of living is very high in gold-producing areas such as Houndé. Consumer goods are expensive, as are plots of land, which in turn leads to high housing costs.

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